

Dimensions of Effective Cybersecurity Training: A Systematic Literature Review

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Abstract. The effectiveness of cybersecurity and cybersecurity awareness training is crucial for organisations and individuals, as both are at risk of cyberattacks that may have serious consequences. A systematic review of 37 articles identified multiple dimensions of the effectiveness of cybersecurity and cybersecurity awareness training. The findings are discussed across four dimensions: user characteristics, training approaches (e.g., interactive, hands-on, industry-specific), and training outcomes (e.g., behavioural changes, decision-making, long-term effects). Lastly, ways to measure the effectiveness of cybersecurity training are explored (e.g., surveys and observation). The findings show that prioritising users and their characteristics in the design and delivery of training is key to its effectiveness. In addition, combinations of different training approaches appear to be more effective.

Keywords: cybersecurity, awareness, training, behaviours, outcomes

1 Introduction

We all face the possibility of becoming victims of a cyberattack, and as a result, the need to ensure that individuals have strong cybersecurity awareness training is increasing. The need for cybersecurity training is not only to protect individuals but also to protect organisations – due to varying levels of end-user knowledge, many incidents and attacks can be linked to end-user behaviour [1], [2].

Understanding how employees respond to cybersecurity incidents is the first step in identifying and mitigating them [3],[1]. Establishing effective communication channels within an organisation can assist, as individuals will know exactly how to report and handle a cybersecurity incident [4]. Also, assisting individuals in identifying and responding to these attacks should be an ongoing, continuous training and learning process [5]. However, conventional awareness training is no longer as effective as it once was [3]. Which types of training are effective, then, and what are the factors influencing their effectiveness? The research question that needs to be answered is therefore: “What are the dimensions of effective cybersecurity training”? This question will be answered through a systematic literature review. (Note that cybersecurity training in this paper includes cybersecurity awareness training.)

The structure of this paper is as follows: Section 2 presents a short literature background, followed by the research method. Section 4 presents the findings. Sections 5 and 6 reflect and conclude the paper. Finally, future research is discussed in Section 7.

2 Literature Background

Prümmer et al. [1] contend that the consequences of cybersecurity attacks are often not immediately detectable, and due to this, individuals and organisations do not prioritise cybersecurity. However, insider threats are a real concern and should be addressed by influencing employee behaviour and engagement through continuous learning [2, 4]. Organisations make use of SETA (Security Education, Training and Awareness) programs, but it is not always successful [6]. The impact and effectiveness of training and awareness programs are also dependent on individuals' prior knowledge and demographics [7]. The fact that cybersecurity training and awareness are not a one-size-fits-all approach leads to differing opinions on which approaches are most effective [1]. The obvious question is, what is the most effective approach to cybersecurity training for a specific context and group? Individuals often have an optimistic view of training and of the training provided [8], but are these approaches really effective?

Implementing consolidated training approaches and methods is one way to ensure effectiveness [3]. But hands-on/experimental training and traditional/theory-based training have been proven to be beneficial as well. A traditional presentation-based approach showed a 15.49% increase in awareness following the training [1]. Also, gamification, the physical application of what has been learnt in theory, and its integration into everyday jobs, helps individuals realise the importance of training [4]. It follows from the above discussion that several factors and dimensions play a role in the effectiveness of cybersecurity training. The question this paper attempts to address, therefore, is *what the dimensions of effective cybersecurity training approaches are*.

3 Research Method

A Systematic Literature Review (SLR) approach was followed, focusing on the effectiveness of cybersecurity training approaches. The SLR process followed the five steps suggested by [9].

3.1 Data sources, search terms and inclusion criteria

Data was gathered from the following databases: 1) EbscoHost, 2) Scopus and 3) Science Direct. The search string applied to all three of the databases was: ("Effectiveness" OR "cybersecurity behaviour change" OR "impact") AND ("cybersecurity training" OR "Cybersecurity awareness training"). Articles were included published between 2020 and 2025, written in English, peer-reviewed conference or journal papers focusing on empirical research. Duplicate articles were removed.

3.2 Data extraction and analysis

Figure 1 (PRISMA Flowchart) includes three sections. During Identification, the database search produced 280 articles. During screening, 33 duplicate articles were removed, then 43 non-empirical studies were removed as well as four articles that were not English. Lastly, 163 articles were removed through the screening process as they did not address the research question of how effective cybersecurity and cybersecurity awareness training is.

Fig. 1. Flowchart created in LucidChart to display articles included in synthesis.

Data extraction has been completed for the final 37 articles, which focused on the review and highlighting titles, abstracts, findings, and conclusions. The inclusion of these articles was based on the contribution to the topic of cybersecurity. The data analysis method used for the SLR was thematic analysis, a qualitative research process for analysing and identifying themes in data [10]. The identified themes are discussed below.

4 Findings

Figure 2 highlights the various themes pertaining to the main research topic. There are 4 main themes that have been identified, with several sub-themes related to the main themes. These themes and the number of papers addressing each are displayed below:

Fig. 2. Total Number of Papers by Themes

4.1 Main Themes relating to Cybersecurity and Awareness Training

User characteristics

The literature indicates that users' **attitudes and perceptions** affect the effectiveness of training. Almost 60% of the world's population uses the internet, yet many users have never received cybersecurity training or are unaware of the risks [11]. Organisations struggle with attacks and security compromises due to user behaviour and non-compliance with policies. As a result, improving user behaviour will lead to sustainable success, because no number of controls on infrastructure or checklists will override bad behaviour [12]. Shillair et al. [11] contend that when a training program is not just focused on technology-savvy users but reaches all users, it can be regarded as effective. Another factor influencing the effectiveness of cybersecurity training is.

Training fatigue and time limitations. Examples include the healthcare industry, where the biggest constraints are capacity and high workload, making cybersecurity training a low priority [13]. Another example is the maritime sector, where a shortage of time, resources and money results in the ineffectiveness of the training [14].

Cultural and demographic factors also have an influence. National culture and demographics influence how individuals handle cybersecurity incidents [15, 16]. For the elderly, specifically individuals aged 75 and above, cybersecurity attacks have risen due to unfamiliarity with the cybersecurity and technological landscape, which increases exposure to potential financial loss and increases the likelihood of being a repeated victim of cyberattacks [15, 16]. It is assumed that younger people are more aware of cybersecurity and the crimes associated with it. Martínez-Peláez et al. [17] have shown that age is not a significant factor and that training should be inclusive

across all age groups and adopt a gender-neutral approach. Another demographic is education: more educated individuals are more knowledgeable about cybersecurity [17].

To conclude, it appears that users are engaged in the training as long as it accommodates individuals in multiple demographics, such as age and education level [16, 17]. The effectiveness of cybersecurity training is influenced by users' attitudes, perceptions, motivation, and cultural and demographic differences; it does not solely lie in technology.

Type of training (Training Approaches)

Several papers indicate the use of **e-learning** in cybersecurity training [18, 19]. Apart from cybersecurity training, e-learning also increases exposure to cyberattacks. As such, it can also be used to raise users' awareness of the cybersecurity risks associated with e-learning [18]. Organisations making use of e-learning or remote-based platforms should integrate training and awareness into the platform so that users are aware and educated on the various risks [18].

Micro-training or Context-Based Micro Training (CBMT) is also implemented. This training is short and directly applicable to the situation that the user is in [20]. It appears that CBMT is perceived as positive across different demographics [6]. When using CBMT, it is important to ensure that all training is up-to-date and frequent, so individuals remain continuously attentive to dynamic change. [21].

Another approach evident in the literature is **interactive and blended training** [21, 22]. A one-size-fits-all or off-the-shelf cybersecurity training approach can leave many users feeling fatigued and discouraged [22]. Determining if individuals are beginners or have prior knowledge is important, therefore combining training is the most effective and influences behavioral change [22]. Tailoring training programs to individuals' learning styles and incorporating buddy systems are effective ways to help individuals learn, feel motivated, and attend training [21]. No training is successful in isolation: Workman [12] shows that relying solely on live activities (capture the flag and hackathons) does not yield impactful outcomes; however, when traditional classroom training is included, outcomes are more successful.

Narrative -based training is also used. Hull et al. [23] show that this method (training through storytelling) is effective as it increases individuals' engagement and curiosity. The storytelling should be simple and straightforward to be effective [21].

Many individuals enjoy the practical element of **hands-on or practical training** because they can relate to the various scenarios. Cyber Range Exercises (CRXs) allow users to experience an actual cybersecurity attack in controlled environments, enabling them to relate to a real-world example [24]. **Gamified training** also shows promising results, leading to positive user perceptions of the training [25].

Sometimes cybersecurity training needs to be tailored to **specific industries**. An example of this is beginners who may require extra support, materials and training sessions [18]. Specifically, in industries with overworked employees, such as healthcare, cybersecurity training programs should be short and engaging [13, 26]. Other industries need specialised training focusing on specific regulations and compliance requirements relating to cybersecurity [14].

In conclusion, training approaches can be a combination of multiple training types, and the specialisation of these different methods can yield positive outcomes for users.

Training Outcomes

The literature indicates that the desired outcome of cybersecurity training has a long-term impact on attitudes and knowledge, leading to increased confidence, increased awareness and compliance. This results in better decision making, detection styles, and changed behaviour.

Long-term attitude and behaviour change result from cybersecurity culture change, driven by how cybersecurity is managed [27]. When organisations implement and integrate cybersecurity training, their main goal should be to change individuals' behaviour and attitudes [21]. Management's support is key to ensuring success in cybersecurity training and initiatives, as this impact filters through the entire organisation, encouraging a culture of responsibility and attentiveness [18, 21]

Cybersecurity training results in **improved knowledge** as an outcome. More knowledge leads to confidence in identifying phishing attacks, breaches, ransomware and understanding the importance of data protection [18, 26]. There is a shortage of cybersecurity professionals; therefore, building knowledge and awareness of users as it relates to cybersecurity is an investment [11], and users will feel more **confident** when quality resources and training are available [28]. Increased knowledge and a positive attitude will lead to changed user behaviour. In this regard, specifically for behaviour change, CBMT performed better and achieved higher scores than individuals who received only game-based training [20]. Chaudhary [21] states that combined approaches have a positive impact on cybersecurity behaviour and motivation to change. Cybersecurity training can boost confidence and positivity, but it can also lead to overconfidence, which can cause problematic behaviours in organisations [29].

More knowledge leads to **greater awareness** of cybersecurity threats [18]. A study showed that those who have received cybersecurity training were less likely to be victims of phishing attacks [27]. Another study found that awareness of cybersecurity policy conformance and compliance improved after individuals received e-learning and simulation-based training [18].

More knowledge also leads to improved **decision-making**. Increased knowledge allows for less reliance on intuitive decision-making and more confidence in knowledge-based decisions, which will assist users in the quick identification of cybersecurity incidents [30]

When individuals are motivated and find cybersecurity training enjoyable, these positive outcomes are easier to reach as they tend to engage more and understand its importance [12]. When training feels fun and enjoyable, users are more likely to complete it [31].

Fallatah et al. [32] used the TAM (Technology Acceptance Model) framework to evaluate training across various factors. Visibility helps users recognise the benefit of training. Voluntariness allows users to decide when to complete training, thereby increasing motivation.

Organisations play an important role in setting the scene for effective cybersecurity training. It is important that organisations prioritise the funding and planning for the

cybersecurity training to be up-to-date and consist of combinations that are effective [28]. Organisations need to cater to emotional elements such as trust, worry, apathy and control because they affect how users engage, and if behaviour isn't changed, then training is ineffective [32]. Alcaide and Llave [33] and Chaudhary [21] mention that there are societal norms that encourage healthy behaviour, the same can go for management that can promote positive behaviour on cybersecurity. The policies in an organisation play a big role as they guide individuals on how to use IT assets safely and how to mitigate or respond to attacks; however, the policies should not overwhelm or cause fatigue [21, 34].

Measurement of Training Effectiveness

The literature reports several methods for measuring the effectiveness of cybersecurity training. For example, the use of **Machine Learning** helped identify different traits leading to overconfidence, such as age, financial standing and motivation to attend training [29].

Surveys and questionnaires are commonly used as a measurement method. It can be used to understand training preference before a training approach is chosen [32]. For example, surveys distributed among critical care staff showed a preference for e-learning (56%) over ward/unit-based training (36%) [13]. Surveys and scenario-based approaches can also be used to identify gaps and help management understand cybersecurity and threats [35, 36]. Questionnaires help determine attitudes and knowledge regarding information security and identify gaps, particularly among the elderly, for which specific training is then required [15, 34]. Surveys can be used as pre- and post-tests. An example is the test of the effectiveness of the Synergistic Cyber Security Awareness Model for the Elderly (SCSAM-Elderly) Model in a user group in Malaysia : the average of the pre-test (40%) improved to an average of 82% in the post-test [15]. Interviews are also used to understand effectiveness. Reeves et al. [22] used interviews to identify emotions and revealed users' frustration when certain training materials were not applicable to their roles, thereby reducing the effectiveness of the training.

Observation is an important measurement instrument. Eye-tracking tools can be used to observe how users engage with and respond to cybersecurity incidents, as they track users' fixation and focus [20]. Wang et al. [37] reported that after PowerPoint training for drivers to respond to cyberattacks on vehicles, the effectiveness was assessed through a driving simulator, where most drivers responded safely by slowing down or exhibiting cautionary behaviours, indicating positive responses to cyberattacks.

Measurement of training effectiveness helps experts determine which method is most effective by using approaches such as modelling and machine learning, surveys, observations, and simulation.

5 Discussion

To answer the research question, the findings are organised according to the dimensions of the Context, Input, Reaction and Outcome (CIRO) Model, as defined by Warr, Bird

and Rackham [38], which is designed to evaluate professional development effectiveness. Table 1 describes the model and maps the 4 themes relating to the effectiveness of cybersecurity training.

Table 1. Mapping of the CIRO Model to Themes

CIRO Model	Definition of Model by Tamkin, Yarnall, Kerrin [39]	Main Theme Identified in this review
Context	Helps understand the requirements and objectives of training	User Characteristics
Input	Research on which of the training is the most appropriate for the desired outcome	Type of Training/ Training Approaches
Reaction	Feedback on how individuals view the training	Measurement of Training Effectiveness
Outcome	Results of the training is evaluated at various levels	Training Outcomes

To design and implement effective cybersecurity training, four dimensions need to be considered, as explained below:

The training **context** is provided by user characteristics. Demographics influence how training needs to be designed so that it caters and addresses requirements for various groups, and it's effective when it is tailored accordingly [22, 30, 32]

The choice of training approach or type of training is part of the **input**. This choice affects how users receive the training, and a one-size-fits-all approach can lead to fatigue and make users feel less motivated to complete it [22]. Combinations of various types of training, such as CBMT, hands-on and gamification training, have positive results as they allow users to experience simulations in an environment that replicates a cybersecurity attack [20]; [30]. Narrative training and gamification promote curiosity and excitement in individuals [23, 25]. Since there are unique challenges in certain sectors, specialised training needs to be created so that users can benefit from it [14]; [13]. **Reaction** to the training refers to how trainees perceived it. It also relates to the training's outcome. If there are positive changes in behaviour and decision-making, and increased knowledge, awareness, and compliance, it can be said that the training had a positive outcome [20]; [26]; [18]. Long-term impacts influence how organisational culture ensures responsibility and accountability for cybersecurity [21], [18]. When training feels fun and enjoyable, users are more likely to complete it.[11].

The **outcome** of the training is measured in different ways. Behavioural change, changed attitudes, improved knowledge, and cybersecurity awareness are measured or evaluated by observing users, using Machine Learning algorithms [29], gathering survey feedback, or conducting simulation attacks [34]; [36]. When users' behaviour has changed, and knowledge has improved, then the outcome of training is positive [21]; [18]. The way users make decisions to cybersecurity attacks is also an important outcome [30]. These outcomes ultimately indicate whether the type or approach of training was successful.

6 Conclusion

The systematic literature review of the effectiveness of cybersecurity training approaches highlighted that cybersecurity training effectiveness depends on various dimensions – the context, the input, the outcome, and the measurement of outcomes. The **context** is provided by users' attitudes, cultural and demographic backgrounds. A sole focus on technical content is not adequate. The human layer is the main form of defence [12, 33]. Taking the context into account influences the **input** (the training approach). Each cybersecurity intervention should be designed to achieve the desired reaction and **outcome** (e.g., better decision-making, a positive attitude towards cybersecurity), and **ways to determine** the effectiveness of the training should be in place (e.g., surveys, observation).

The SLR revealed gaps in the literature, including variation in the scope, methodology, and context of the studies, which made direct comparisons difficult. Measurement of training effectiveness showed that surveys and questionnaires were the most popular measurement tools across the studies, though they are subjective. There are gaps in the study regarding specific training for different demographics and the development of tailored programs. In conclusion, prioritising users and their characteristics in the design and delivery of training is key to its effectiveness.

7 Recommended Future Research

Future research can focus on the design and selection of training programs for specific audiences (e.g., different age groups, educational levels, and cultural backgrounds). Research by [15–17] concluded that specific training would need to be designed for different demographics, but it does not provide any details on how to do so. In addition, more research is needed on the best combination of different training approaches (e.g., micro-training, gamification) for different roles within an organisation. Findings from this study indicated that no single training approach is effective on its own [12].

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